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Examining The Investment Opportunities Presented By Urbanization In The Real Estate Sector Of Bonny Island, Rivers State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Urbanization has emerged as a critical driver of real estate investment dynamics in rapidly developing coastal regions of Nigeria. This study examined the investment opportunities presented by urbanization in the real estate sector of Bonny Island, Rivers State. The research evaluated how population growth, expanding economic activities, infrastructural development, and industrial concentration: particularly oil and gas operations; have influenced demand for residential, commercial, and mixed-use properties. Using a mixed-methods approach, data were obtained through structured questionnaires, interviews with key stakeholders; A mixed-methods approach was adopted, using structured questionnaires were administered to 384 stakeholders, of which 269 valid responses were analyzed representing an 70% response rate. Descriptive analytical techniques (frequency, mean, RII) were employed to assess emerging investment patterns and opportunities. The findings revealed that urbanization has significantly increased land values, rental demand, and property development activities, particularly in residential housing, commercial spaces, and supporting service infrastructure. However, challenges such as inadequate urban planning, infrastructure deficits, and regulatory constraints limit optimal investment outcomes. The study concludes that strategic urban management, improved infrastructure provision, and supportive policy frameworks are essential for maximizing real estate investment opportunities in Bonny Island.

Keywords: Urbanization; Real Estate Investment; Property Development; Infrastructure; Bonny Island.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Urbanization has emerged as one of the most transformative demographic trends shaping spatial development, socio-economic systems, and investment landscapes across developing economies. In Nigeria, rapid urban expansion has intensified since the early 2000s, driven by population growth, rural-urban migration, industrialization, and infrastructural development ((Nkpite & Oba, 2024; National Population Commission, 2023; Aderamo & Obembe, 2021). This accelerated urban growth continues to redefine the structure and dynamics of settlements, influencing land-use patterns, housing demand, and the broader real estate market. As urban centres expand, they often generate new economic activities, attract investment, and stimulate infrastructural upgrades that create favorable conditions for real estate development and investment (UN-Habitat, 2020; World Bank, 2022).

In the Niger Delta region: an area traditionally known for its oil and gas activities; urbanization presents unique opportunities for real estate investors due to the interplay of economic activities, infrastructural expansion, and increasing population pressure (Ejumudo, 2014). Bonny Island in Rivers State stands out as a rapidly urbanizing locality, driven mainly by industrial operations such as those of the Nigeria LNG

Limited and associated multinational oil and gas firms. These developments have spurred a steady inflow of workers, heightened housing demand, and stimulated the expansion of commercial and residential property markets (Nwankwo & Ezenwa, 2022). As a result, Bonny Island has witnessed a rise in land values, increased private sector participation in property development, and the emergence of new investment corridors.

Despite these developments, scholarly attention on the specific investment opportunities created by urbanization in Bonny Island remains limited. Most existing studies on urbanization in Nigeria focus on metropolitan centres such as Port Harcourt, Lagos, and Abuja (Adewale, 2021; Iwuanyanwu & Nwosu, 2019), leaving a gap in understanding how smaller but economically strategic zones like Bonny Island are evolving. Therefore, a focused examination of the opportunities emerging from the island's urban transformation is essential for guiding policymakers, investors, and stakeholders in the real estate sector. This study examines the investment opportunities presented by urbanization in the real estate sector of Bonny Island, Rivers State. It highlights the mechanisms through which urban expansion shapes property demand, land-use dynamics, and market profitability, thereby contributing to the discourse on sustainable urban development and real estate investment in Nigeria.

1.1 Aim and Objectives of the Study

The purpose of this study is to examine the real estate investment opportunities created by urbanization that enhance real estate development and investment prospects in Bonny Island, Rivers State, Nigeria. While specific objectives are to:

- i. Assess types of real estate investment opportunities in Bonny Island
- ii. Identify most real estate investment opportunities created by urbanization in Bonny Island

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Urbanization triggers a range of structural and spatial transformations that create investment opportunities in the real estate sector. Rapid population growth in cities leads to increased demand for housing, retail spaces, educational and health facilities, and transportation infrastructure (Henderson, 2010). These needs stimulate real estate development, particularly in peri-urban and newly urbanizing areas. According to Adetunji and Olamiju (2019), Nigerian cities such as Lagos, Abuja, and Port Harcourt have experienced substantial real estate booms in response to high levels of urbanization, with informal settlements and real estate speculation being major features of these expansions. In cities like Bonny Island, the presence of industrial projects (Nigeria LNG) has accelerated migration and urbanization, thereby attracting real estate investors to meet the growing residential and commercial needs (Kok, Monkkonen & Quigley, 2014). Additionally, urbanization influences land value appreciation, one of the critical drivers of real estate investment. As urban centers expand, land located near city centers or along transport corridors becomes more valuable, motivating private and institutional investors to invest in those locations (Nkpote & Oba, 2024; Kok et al., 2014).

2.1 Investment Opportunities Presented by Urbanization in Real Estate Sector

Bonny Island has undergone rapid urban growth driven by industrialization and the expansion of oil and gas activities. Population growth and workforce migration have resulted in increased demand for housing, commercial spaces, and urban infrastructure, creating opportunities for real estate investment (Obafemi, 2019). However, population growth and workforce inflows have created a significant housing demand on Bonny Island. Investment opportunities exist in developing multi-family apartments, gated communities, serviced estates, and affordable housing schemes (Nkpote & Oba, 2024). The influx of industrial workers has also fueled demand for mid-market and premium housing segments (Jumbo, 2024). Studies has found that urbanization stimulates demand for office spaces, retail complexes, hotels, and mixed-use developments. The rising middle class, increased disposable incomes, and consumer demand have enhanced commercial real estate viability, attracting both domestic and international investors (Aminigbo, 2025).

Another opportunity created by urbanization is infrastructure expansion and investment potential. Infrastructure developments, including roads, bridges, utilities, and transport networks, improve land accessibility and increase property values. Adequate infrastructure enhances the attractiveness of Bonny

Island for real estate investment, supporting higher occupancy rates and long-term profitability (Rivers State Government, 2021; Nwokoro & Chukwueke, 2021). Industrial hubs on Bonny Island, particularly in oil and gas, generate demand for residential, commercial, and hospitality facilities. Urbanization further amplifies opportunities for retail, healthcare, and educational developments to cater to growing urban populations (Allison & Kakulu, 2018).

Mixed-use development and urban redevelopment have been an opportunity created by urbanization in most Nigerian urban centres (Aminigbo, 2025). Urbanization encourages redevelopment of aging urban areas and creation of mixed-use projects. Brownfield regeneration, waterfront development, and commercial-residential integrated developments attract investors seeking long-term returns (Federal Ministry of Environment, 2021). Nevertheless, socio-economic factors and market expansion from urbanization contributes to socio-economic growth; diversification of employment opportunities, and improved income levels, enhancing demand for modern housing, commercial, and mixed-use properties (Nkpote & Oba, 2024). These socio-economic improvements create a favorable environment for real estate investment (Obafemi, 2019).

Urbanization and its effects on real estate development have been the subject of several scholarly investigations. Allison and Kakulu (2018) examined the challenges of traditional land delineation practices in Bonny, emphasizing the administrative and legal obstacles affecting land development. Aminigbo (2025) focused on climate change-driven coastal and shoreline changes in Rivers State, highlighting environmental risks that could impact real estate values and investment decisions. Nwokoro and Chukwueke (2021) discussed broader land administration challenges in Nigeria, identifying tenure insecurity and bureaucratic inefficiencies as key impediments to sustainable property development. Obafemi (2019) analyzed the effects of urbanization on housing for the urban poor in Port Harcourt, emphasizing affordability and socio-economic pressures that limit access to formal housing. Further studies, such as Aderamo and Obembe (2021) and Adewale (2021), explored the relationship between urban growth, housing demand, and infrastructure development in Nigerian urban centers, pointing out constraints in planning, governance, and service provision. Ejumudo (2014) highlighted urbanization-induced challenges such as informal settlements, environmental degradation, and inadequate social amenities, while Iwuanyanwu and Nwosu (2019) examined real estate investment dynamics within rapidly urbanizing areas, focusing on market trends and financial viability. Nwankwo and Ezenwa (2022) analyzed investment potential and policy frameworks for real estate in Rivers State, emphasizing the role of strategic urban planning.

Although these studies provide valuable insights into land administration, environmental risks, housing, infrastructure, and investment in Nigeria broadly, there is limited research that specifically examines the investment opportunities emerging from urbanization on Bonny Island, particularly within its unique industrial, socio-economic, and infrastructural context. Most previous studies either focus on Port Harcourt, general Rivers State, or thematic challenges such as climate risk or land tenure. None provide a comprehensive analysis of the emerging real estate investment prospects created by urbanization in Bonny Island, considering both market dynamics and strategic opportunities. The present study addresses this gap by exploring the investment opportunities presented by urbanization in the real estate sector of Bonny Island, offering targeted insights for developers, investors, and policymakers seeking to capitalize on the island's growing urban and industrial landscape.

3. 0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study is conducted in Bonny Island, located in Rivers State, Nigeria, is a coastal island in the Niger Delta with growing urbanization due to oil, gas, and industrial activities. It features ecologically sensitive mangroves, estuarine landscapes, and developing infrastructure, making it a strategic area for real estate investment. This study employed a descriptive survey research design combining the mixed-methods approach to collect data from stakeholders involved in urban development including property developers, investors, and government officials. Both quantitative and qualitative data were collected using purposive and stratified random sampling, 384 respondents were selected. Out of these; 269 valid responses were retrieved, representing an 70% response rate. Data were collected using structured questionnaires based

on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree; 5 = Strongly Agree). Open-ended questions complemented the quantitative data. Descriptive statistics (frequency, mean and RII ranking) were used to rank real estate investment opportunities to support investment trend identification. Qualitative data were analyzed using thematic content analysis to identify investment opportunities, infrastructural constraints, and environmental considerations.

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Real Estate Investment Opportunities in Bonny Island

Figure 1 showed the real estate investment opportunities linked to urbanization in Bonny Island. As shown in Figure 1; 24% of the respondents agreed that residential real estate is an opportunity of investment, while 20% indicated as commercial, 16% as industrial, 22% as mixed-use developments, and 18% land speculative investment.

Figure 1: Real Estate Investment Opportunities in Bonny Island
 Source: Author’s Field Survey, 2025.

The study revealed that residential real estate occurs due to rising population and employment in industrial sectors driven demand for low- to medium-income housing, gated communities, and rental apartments. While the commercial real estate arises from growth in services, retail, and office spaces supports investment in commercial properties. Mixed-use developments were integrated into residential and commercial properties to meet urban lifestyle needs while providing diversified income streams for investors. As the acquisition of undeveloped land along planned infrastructure corridors offers potential capital appreciation. Population inflows driven by industrial expansion have created high demand for residential properties. Investors report rising rental yields, particularly for medium-density apartments and gated communities. Residential real estate is the most immediate opportunity for investors due to demand-supply gaps. The emergence of new businesses, retail outlets, and service providers presents opportunities for commercial and mixed-use properties. Mixed-use developments attract both residential and commercial tenants, offering diversified income streams and mitigating investment risk. Strategically located undeveloped land along proposed infrastructure corridors, particularly near the mainland connection and industrial hubs, offers high potential for capital appreciation. Early acquisition allows investors to benefit from rising demand and property value growth. The planned road connections, improved utilities, and industrial park expansion serve as critical enablers for real estate investment. Infrastructure improvements enhance property accessibility and market attractiveness, stimulating investor confidence. It implies that urbanization in Bonny Island generated substantial investment

opportunities across residential, commercial, industrial, and mixed-use real estate markets. Population growth, economic expansion, infrastructure development, and socio-economic improvements position Bonny Island as a promising destination for profitable real estate ventures. Strategic planning, stakeholder collaboration, and careful market analysis are necessary to maximize returns and ensure sustainable development.

4.2 Real Estate Opportunities Created by Urbanization in Bonny Island

Table 1 presented ranked topper most real estate opportunities created by urbanization in the context of real estate investment in Bonny Island.

Table 1: Ranking of Real Estate Opportunities Created by Urbanization

Opportunity	SD	D	N	A	SA	MS	Std. Dev.	RII	Rank
Increased demand for residential housing	5	10	15	70	169	4.44	0.90	0.89	1 st
Appreciation of land values	7	15	20	80	147	4.28	1.00	0.86	2 nd
Development of rental/multi-unit properties	10	18	25	90	126	4.13	1.07	0.83	3 rd
Emergence of new commercial corridors	12	20	30	100	107	4.13	1.03	0.82	4 th
Expansion of formal/informal housing markets	15	25	35	85	109	4.00	1.10	0.80	5 th
Increased infrastructure-driven development	8	18	27	95	121	3.98	1.09	0.79	6 th
Growth in investor interest and participation	20	40	50	100	59	3.92	1.18	0.78	7 th

Source: Author’s Field Survey, 2025.

As presented in Table1; majority (Mean Score >3.00; RII>0.60) of respondents strongly agree that urbanization has led to significant increased demand for housing, land value appreciation, expansion of formal/informal housing markets, infrastructure-driven development, growing investor interest and emergence of commercial corridors. As presented in Table1; more than half of the respondents with mean >3.00; RII>0.60 overwhelmingly agreed that demand for residential housing is on the increase, land value appreciation, expansion of formal/informal housing markets, infrastructure-driven development, growing investor interest and emergence of commercial corridors. These are the most prominent real estate investment opportunities emerging in Bonny Island, particularly around Finima, Bonny Town, and areas near the LNG plant, has been experiencing value increases due to infrastructural investments, port activities, and limited supply. This reflected dual demand pressures of investors seeking affordable rentals/multi-units and expansion of commercial corridors. The findings affirmed that developers are responding to urban population pressures by constructing apartments, gated estates, and mixed-income housing schemes. However, this has triggered growth in informal settlements alongside planned estates; especially for low-income earners requiring low-cost housing development with challenges of slum expansion due to unregulated migration.

Infrastructure projects (roads, bridges, seaport facilities, utilities) create opportunities for site-and-service developments and property price escalation (mean = 3.92; RII = 0.784). Despite being an opportunity for real estate, the respondents suggested seen it as less sustainable compared to formal housing demand. While investor interest is growing (local elites, corporate staff, external investors), the relatively low mean suggests investment confidence is still cautious. With the investor interest and participation (mean 3.92; RII = 0.784) possible reasons were based on security concerns, land tenure conflicts, infrastructure deficits, and dependence on oil economy (volatility). The findings revealed that suburban area of Bonny Island have experienced an increase in industrial estate development, partly due to proximity to ports, transport infrastructure, and large labor markets.

In the context of Bonny Island, overall trend of urbanization showed that it primarily creates residential and land-based opportunities, followed by commercial and rental markets, while infrastructure and investor participation are emerging but less dominant. The implication for real estate investment is that, developers should prioritize residential housing projects and land banking strategies. As the rise of commercial corridors presents an opportunity for mixed-use developments. And government-private sector collaboration is crucial to turn infrastructure projects into real estate growth catalysts. Contextually, Bonny's role reflecting as a strategic oil and gas hub (NLNG, Shell, etc.) directly fuels demand for housing, land, and commerce. However, unless policy, security, and infrastructural gaps are addressed, investor participation will remain limited.

However, the interview results revealed that housing demand (87.3%) is the most universally agreed driver of real estate opportunities in Bonny, reflecting migration from rural hinterlands and workforce influx linked to the oil and gas industry. Housing demand emerged as the strongest driver, linked to the influx of oil workers, population migration, and limited housing stock. This reveals a sustainable opportunity for residential development and rental investments. With 75.6% responses, the respondents indicated the recognition of new commercial corridors) indicates that urbanization is not just residential but is restructuring land use into mixed-use corridors, particularly around Finima, Bonny Main Town, and road linkages to LNG facilities. This is reflection of urbanization reshaping Bonny's spatial economy by creating new commercial nodes. As these new corridors support retail, hospitality, and service industries, generating secondary real estate opportunities beyond residential housing. Urbanization, coupled with infrastructure development (roads, bridges, and port expansion), is intensifying competition for strategically located land parcels. Whereby infrastructure development acts as a catalyst for both land value appreciation and commercial property growth. Improved accessibility makes remote land viable for development. While the oil and gas industry's expansion create ripple effects in real estate; housing, commercial facilities, and supporting social infrastructure. This strengthens the long-term viability of property investments. The thematic results revealed that Bonny Island's urbanization is not a singular trend but a complex interplay of industrial growth, demographic shifts, and infrastructural investments.

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Urbanization driven by industrial expansion, infrastructural planning, and population inflow presents significant investment opportunities for the real estate sector in Bonny Island. Residential housing, mixed-use developments, land banking, and commercial real estate all appear promising, especially if timed with infrastructural improvements and managed with sustainability in mind. The study has demonstrated that urbanization presents substantial investment opportunities in the real estate sector of Bonny Island, driven by population influx, economic expansion, and industrial activities. Increased demand for residential, commercial, and mixed-use developments has enhanced property values and investment returns, positioning Bonny Island as a growing real estate investment destination within Rivers State. Despite these opportunities, persistent challenges related to infrastructure inadequacy, land-use planning inefficiencies, and regulatory constraints continue to affect investment sustainability. However, potential investors must remain aware of environmental risks, infrastructure delays, regulatory uncertainties, and demand volatility. With careful planning, due diligence, and sustainable development practices, Bonny Island could emerge as a viable and attractive real estate investment frontier beyond traditional oil-and-gas investments. Addressing these challenges through proactive urban planning, improved infrastructure delivery, and investor-friendly policies will be critical to harnessing the full potential of urbanization-induced real estate investments. The study therefore underscored the need for coordinated efforts among government, private investors, and community stakeholders to promote sustainable and inclusive real estate development in Bonny Island.

Based on the results, the following recommendations are proposed for investors, policymakers, and researchers:

- a. **Early Land Acquisition:** Investors should consider acquiring land early along planned infrastructural corridors (Bodo-Bonny expressway, proposed mainland link); but should conduct due diligence on land titles, environmental suitability, and future zoning regulations.

- b. **Sustainable Development:** Real estate developers should incorporate climate-resilient design principles: flood mitigation, proper drainage, soil stabilization, sustainable drainage systems, and environmentally compliant materials; particularly given Bonny's coastal/wetland context.
- c. **Mixed-Use Development:** Developers and investors should develop integrated residential-commercial projects to cater for both housing demand and the rising need for retail, services, and amenities for a growing population; to maximize rental yields and market appeal.
- d. **Stakeholder Engagement:** Developers must collaborate with local authorities, traditional institutions, and communities to facilitate project approvals and compliance; by ensuring social acceptability, benefit sharing, and sustainable urban growth.
- e. **Policy Support:** Government should streamline land administration, improve infrastructure, and provide incentives for sustainable real estate investment.

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